

Sequential decisions in digital agriculture - A cybernet- ICS perspective

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Abstract

As digital technology starts to disrupt the agricultural sector and it becomes feasible to generate appropriate data, there is a great opportunity for developing and deploying novel decision and system-theory tools to assist with the management of agricultural processes as well as whole food-production systems. Agricultural Cybernetics takes a system view of agricultural production for the analysis and design of management strategies to control, optimise, and make crop behaviours of agricultural production systems robust while exploiting the intrinsic feedback information-exchanging mechanisms that these systems exhibit. Feedback is a powerful tool, but it is also subject to fundamental limitations, which when poorly understood can lead to underwhelming results as well as wasting time and resources. Cybernetics provides proven tools and processes to answer fundamental system-related questions that are directly applicable to agriculture: Can we achieve desired crop system behaviours given particular means to act on the system? Is it possible to extract the required information from the data collected? Conversely, what is the adequate infrastructure for data generation given the information requirements related to management? Is the management strategy robust to different sources of uncertainty associated with data, mathematical models and knowledge used in the analytics? The key to answering these questions lies in understanding concepts related to the characterisation of uncertainty, information, decision problems, and how system-feedback structures process information. This paper points to key system concepts applicable to in-season management of crops whereby a sequence of decisions have to be made as part of the management strategy. This relates, for example, to activities such as irrigation, nutrition, and pest-and-disease management. It discusses the potential use of cybernetics tools for analysing and solving these management problems. The material presented has a bearing on the choice and design of infrastructure for data generation, the adoption of data analytics, the formulation of decision problems, and the potential effectiveness and robustness of management strategies, and their return on investment.

Background

One of the fundamental activities in farming is decision making. It is estimated, for example, that crop farmers make over 70 different decisions during a crop season. These decisions relate to crop planning, in-season management, harvest and post-harvest, and business. In this paper, we concentrate on in-season management decisions. This involves a process whereby decisions are made in sequence and the objective is to achieve desired crop behaviours during the season while taking into account the delayed response of the crop to the implemented actions and the interactions between the system and its environment which are uncertain and cannot be influenced by the in-season management strategy. For example, this is the case in irrigation, nutrition, and pest-and-disease management.

Figure 1 shows a representation of a cropping system—a delimited collection of interacting components (crop, soil, and pest and diseases). Such a system is affected by interactions with the environment like weather and the introduction of pathogens. The system is also affected by the actions implemented as the result of decision making associated with management. In order to make these decisions, it is important to consider

- the underlying management problem and its constraints;
- the key information and knowledge about the system;
- the strategies to solve the decision problem leading to the actions to be implemented.

In sequential decision problems, most solution strategies are procedures that translate the available information into the actions. The information is extracted from purposefully collected data through the use of data analytics. This defines a feedback loop—as indicated in Figure 1—which must be used at a required rate in order to update the actions based on the most current information.

Feedback is a formidable tool that allows us to achieve three key things: to modify system behaviours, to attain desirable ones, and to maintain behaviours in the face of uncertainty. By behaviour we mean, in broad terms, how the system responds to its environment—we will provide a more formal definition in the next section.

Figure 1. Feedback control of crop systems

Cybernetics deals with the analysis and design of systems that have a feedback structure whether naturally or imposed (Wiener, 1961). In the crop system shown in Figure 1, there are natural feedback mechanisms that capture the interactions between crop, soil, and pests and diseases (indicated with solid arrows in Figure 1), and there is also an imposed feedback structure due to the management strategy. Feedback control and data analytic strategies are the subject of fundamental performance limitations of which the analyst and the designer must be aware in order to avoid undesirable behaviours and the unnecessary waste of time and resources (Seron et al., 1997).

In the next section of the paper, we discuss how to formulate sequential decision problems and point to specific questions related to the possibility of finding solutions to these problems and point to tools in mathematical control theory that can help to find answers. The key to answering these questions lies in the understanding of concepts related to the characterisation of uncertainty, information, decision problems, and how system- feedback structures process information. The material discussed has a bearing on the choice and design of infrastructure for data generation, the adoption of data analytics, the formulation of decision problems, and the potential effectiveness and robustness of management strategies, and their return on investment.

Agriculture Systems - Concepts, Models and Behaviours

Crops are dynamical systems. That is, systems that exhibit responses in which time plays a key role (Polderman and Willems, 1998). This is typical of systems where there is storage of energy, matter, and information. Such systems can be described in terms of a mathematical model of the form

$$\frac{dx(t)}{dt} = F(x(t), u(t), d(t)), \quad (1)$$

where $x(t)$ is a multidimensional variable that describes the state of the system, $u(t)$ is a multidimensional variable that describes the input to the model that consists of the actions resulting from the management, and $d(t)$ is a multidimensional variable that represents the external effects of the environment on the system. The model (1) is referred to as a state-space model. This form of model is widely used in the agricultural science literature—see Thronley and France (2007) and Wallach et al. (2014).

For example, in a simplified model related to irrigation decisions, we can consider: $x(t) = [x_1(t), x_2(t)]$, where $x_1(t)$ is the crop water intake, and $x_2(t)$ is the soil water moisture; $u(t)$ is the irrigation water; and $d(t) = [d_1(t), d_2(t)]$, where $d_1(t)$ is the precipitation, and $d_2(t)$ can be the reference evapotranspiration that relates to temperature, humidity, wind, and solar radiation. If we consider the problem of pest and disease management, the states, the inputs, and environment interactions will change, but the general abstract form of the model (1) will remain the same.

Oftentimes, the model (1) is considered at discrete time intervals $t_k = kT$ where $k = 1, 2, 3, \dots, N$, and, depending of the problem, the time interval T considered can be a second, a minute, an hour, or a day. This leads to the discrete-time state-space model:

$$x_{k+1} = f_k(x_k, u_k), \quad (2)$$

where x_k represents the value of $x(t)$ for $t = t_k = kT$, and similarly for the other variables. Note that we have included the effect of the environment as a change in the function f_k at each stage k . That is, the effect of dk is embedded in f_k .

In order to represent the situation depicted in Figure 1, we need to add another component to the state model. This is called the *measurement model*, which relates the state and the input to the output data that results from what can be measured from the system:

$$y_k = g_k(x_k, u_k), \quad (3)$$

where y_k is a multidimensional variable that represents the measurement at the time $t_k = kT$.

The combination of the state-space model (2) and the measurement model (3) form what is known as the *Input-state-output (i-s-o) model* (Sontag, 1998; Polderman and Willems, 1998).

Now we are in a condition to define a *behaviour B* as a restriction on the values that sequences u_k and y_k for $k = 1, \dots, N$ can take, namely if $u_k \in U$ and $y_k \in Y$, then $B \subseteq Y \times U$, and that restriction is given by the need of u_k and y_k to satisfy the model equations (2) and (3) (Polderman and Willems, 1998).

Sequential Decision Problems to Achieve Desired Behaviours

Now that we have casted the system in terms of the i-s-o model (2) and (3), we can attempt to seek the control-action sequence u_1, u_2, \dots, u_N such that the system exhibits a desired behaviour. Such behaviour can be captured in terms of an *objective function* of the form

$$\begin{aligned} J(u_1, u_2, \dots, u_N) &= J_N(x_N) + \sum_{k=1}^{N-1} J_k(x_k, u_k) \\ &= J_1(x_1, u_1) + J_2(x_2, u_2) + \dots + J_{N-1}(x_{N-1}, u_{N-1}) + J_N(x_N). \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

This objective function takes a different value for each control-action sequence. The objective function has terminal component $J_N(x_N)$ that can capture whether the final state reaches a desired set, and it also has a component at each stage $J_k(x_k, u_k)$ that captures deviations from the desired system response and costs at each stage. For example, $J_N(x_N)$ can represent end of the season yield and crop quality, while $J_k(x_k, u_k)$ can capture input costs, environmental costs, and deviation from expected crop development.

For example, in an irrigation decision context, each stage may represent deviations from the desired soil- moisture profile associated with the different growth stages of the crop and also include the cost of water use.

Since the objective function (4) captures deviations from desired response and costs, we can then define the following problem:

Optimal Management Problem (OMP): Find the sequence u_1, u_2, \dots, u_N that minimises the objective (4) subject to the constraint that (2) must be satisfied together with additional constraints of the form $h_k(u_k) \leq 0$.

The constraints $h_k(u_k) \leq 0$ take into account that there may be restrictions on how much and at which rate inputs can be applied at each stage. For example, in irrigation there may be restrictions associated with water use and at what rate the infrastructure constrains water delivery to the crop. Similar constraints apply to problems of nutrition and pest and disease management.

The OMP defines a desired optimal behaviour by seeking to minimise deviations from the desired performance and input and environmental costs—we use the general term *cost function* to refer to (4). The optimal behaviour is defined implicitly through the choice of the functions $J_N(\cdot)$ and $J_k(\cdot, \cdot)$ and the minimisation of (4). We should highlight the behaviour is only optimal inasmuch as it optimises the objective function. If this function does not capture the real needs of the management problem, then an optimal result may be rather underwhelming.

Note that the OMP is a sequential decision problem, since at each stage we need to find the best action u_k . The problem thus defined takes also into account that there is a cost associated with the whole sequence u_1, u_2, \dots, u_N rather than a single stage, and this is captured by the form of the objective function (4), which adds the cost from each stage. In this case, one must balance the desire to reduce the cost at a single stage against reducing the objective function for the whole sequence. The problem also takes into account that the evolution of the state depends not only on the input but also on the current value of the state, and this is captured by the need of satisfying (2), which is a dynamic model.

The solution of the OMP we seek is often in the form of a feedback strategy that assigns the value of the actions based on the value of the state:

$$u_k = \mu(x_k), \quad (5)$$

for $k = 1, 2, \dots, N$. It is outside the scope of this paper to discuss the methods by which such a solution can be found, and the interested reader should consult, for example, (Bertsekas, 2000).

If models were perfect and we had absolute certainty about future interactions between the crop system and the environment, then we could solve the problem at the beginning of the time horizon and simply apply the sequence of actions u_1, u_2, \dots, u_N throughout the time horizon considered. This would give exactly the same results as the strategy (5). The reason for seeking a solution of the form (5) is that models are seldom perfect and thus this strategy determines the action based on the latest value of the state. This often results in lower values of the objective function—the difference is known as the *value of information* (Bertsekas, 2000).

The type of problem described above is often hard for humans to solve in an optimal way, but very easy for computers. The challenge is to obtain all the different ingredients—the i-s-o model, the objective function, and the constraints. All this goes under the banner of modelling within this particular context.

Incomplete Information and Data Analytics

In order to define data analytics we first need to conceptualise the difference between data, context, and information (French et al., 2009):

- Data describes the aggregate of all data available, namely, either measurements generated by sensors and that gathered from other sources;
- Context describes knowledge that is relevant to the underlying process that generates the data and the decision problem within which one seeks to analyse the data. Part of this knowledge often is embodied in the i-s-o model and the desired behaviour;
- Information describes data organised and summarised such that it is useful within a context. These data can be either a subset of the sensor and gathered data or new data generated through the data analytics.

We can then think of *Data Analytics* as the process that combines *Data* and *Context* to generate *Information*:

$$\text{Data Analytics: } (Data, Context) \rightarrow Information. \quad (6)$$

Within an irrigation decision context, for example, Data could include sensor data, daily records of irrigation water use, as well as weather data retrieved from the Bureau of Meteorology and satellite imagery should this be available. The *Context* includes a water-balance model for the crop-root zone, including model components of crop evapotranspiration and crop growth, surface run-off, and deep drainage. *Information* can be soil moisture in the root zone (which may be available through sensing) and crop evapotranspiration (new data generated by the data analytics process).

In the sequential decision problem considered in the previous section, the state is the required information.

Hence, the form of the feedback strategy (5). This is property of the model (2) in which the state summarises all the past information related to the system.

In many problems, the state cannot be measured directly, and the data available y_k is related to the state through the measurement model (3). The models used in the data analytics are often of the form

$$x_{k+1} = f_k(x_k, u_k) + \eta_k, \quad (7)$$

$$y_k = g_k(x_k, u_k) + E_t, \quad (8)$$

where the variables η_k and ϵ_k represent the state-transition and measurement model errors respectively. These characterise our uncertainty about the different component of the models. This uncertainty can be represented by probability distributions; however, this is not the only characterisation available. For example other approaches represent the uncertainty in terms of a variable that is unknown by bounded—this is known as *set-membership description of uncertainty* Bertsekas (2000). Here, we adopt the probabilistic description with the view that a probability distribution represents our uncertainty about a phenomenon, and not that the phenomenon is random (Jaynes, 2003).

The data analytics then use the model (7)-(8) to determine the marginal probability distribution of the state, namely, $p(x_k | u_k, y_k)$ from which we can then obtain an estimate of the state \hat{x}_k (often the mean or the median):

$$p(x_k | u_k, y_k) \rightarrow \hat{x}_k. \quad (9)$$

The estimate \hat{x}_k can then be used in the feedback strategy (5)—this is a practical solution which may not always lead to an optimal result (Bertsekas, 2000).

The actual form of the data analytics is beyond the scope of this paper, and it suffices to say that a natural way of thinking about these analytics given the sequential nature of the data available is according to the Bayesian perspective. The interested reader should consult Doucet et al. (2001) and Arulampalam et al. (2002) for discussions on sequential Bayesian estimation.

Agricultural Cybernetics

So far we have discussed how in-season management strategies for crops can be described as sequential decision problems in which we seek to minimise an objective function that captures deviations from the desired performance and costs, which can not only relate to input costs but also to sustainability. We have also indicated that the solution of the sequential decision problem often takes the form of a feedback strategy (5) and that practical solutions use data analytics to infer the state of the system, which is the information needed in the type of decisions considered. The design of feedback strategies and sequential data analytics are at the core of Cybernetics. We now move on to key questions related to analysis that are also part of Cybernetics— all of which relate to system properties and thus the material presented in the preceding sections:

Q1 : Can we achieve desired system behaviours given particular means to act?

Q2 : Is it possible to extract the required information from the data collected?

Q3 : Is it possible to diagnose system anomalous behaviours or faults?

Q4 : Is a management strategy robust to different sources of uncertainty?

Question Q1 relates to the system concept of reachability of state models of the form (2). That is whether a state x_j at the stage j can be steered to a state x_k at the stage $k > j$ by a sequence of feasible actions u_j, u_{j+1}, \dots, u_k . This is a property that depends on the particular structure of the function $f_k(\cdot, \cdot)$ in (2). For some systems, there exist tools that look at properties of operators related to $f_k(\cdot, \cdot)$ that determine reachability—see Sontag (1998). Being able to study this property can determine whether one could potentially find a solution to an OMP without having to implement a solution and then finding out that the desired behaviours cannot be achieved—a rather costly exercise.

Question Q2 relates to the system concept of observability. We have indicated in the previous section that with knowledge of the state and measurement models (7)-(8) we could design analytics to obtain the probability distribution of the state $p(x_k | u_k, y_k)$. The feasibility of such a design depends on the structure of both $f_k(\cdot, \cdot)$ and $g_k(\cdot, \cdot)$ in (7)-(8). Roughly speaking, observability means that information about the state can be recovered, in principle, from the measurement (Sontag, 1998). The structure of the models (7)-(8) can impose fundamental limitations, which would impede the development of certain data analytics. These limitations can often be relaxed by adding data from various and different sensors, which in turn modifies the structure of the measurement model $g_k(\cdot, \cdot)$ in (8). For some systems there exist tools that look at properties of operators related to $f_k(\cdot, \cdot)$ and $g_k(\cdot, \cdot)$ that determine observability—see Sontag (1998). Understanding this, it is key to designing appropriate sensing infrastructure. One key question is given $f_k(\cdot, \cdot)$, what is the minimum amount of data that $g_k(\cdot, \cdot)$ should provide in order to be able to infer the non-measured quantities of interest? This has a bearing on the design of data capture infrastructure. Whilst the trend in many sectors is to collect as much data as possible, collecting data in agriculture is expensive; and therefore, is it convenient to know what is the minimum set of data and enable the appropriate output of the data analytics.

Question Q3 relates also to fault diagnosis, which in turn relates also to the system concept of observability discussed in the previous paragraph. A fault is an event in which a system transitions from a nominal or standard behaviour to an anomalous behaviour in which performance often degrades. Depending on the structure of $f_k(\cdot, \cdot)$ and $g_k(\cdot, \cdot)$, we may be able to design analytics to detect system-anomalous behaviours. Some of these faults may not only be detectable, but also identifiable; that is, we could find out where in the system the fault is and how severe it is. Our ability to do this depends on the structure of $f_k(\cdot, \cdot)$ and $g_k(\cdot, \cdot)$ (what sensing modalities we have or make available) as well as the type of fault considered. Understanding the limitations of diagnosis and its implementation is a fundamental enabling factor for the development of intervention strategies for controlling pests and diseases as well as faults in irrigation infrastructure.

Question Q4 relates to the concept of robustness or handling of certain levels of uncertainty. Feedback strategies provide robustness to model uncertainty. The fact that measurements can be used at an appropriate rate with feedback, often results in the need of models that only capture the essential features of the phenomena they seek to describe. Hence, for some management problems, there may be an opportunity for developing simpler models for on-line implementation of feedback structures and data analytics. That is, these models do not necessarily have to have the same fidelity of the models currently used in agri-science like for example in Keating et al. (2003).

Discussion

This paper presents a particular perspective on sequential decision problems, like those associated with in-season crop management. It introduces a Cybernetics perspective that highlights matters related to data, information, and how systems with feedback structure process this information. The increasing availability of data and the potential to harness the benefits of digital technologies in agriculture provide a pivotal point at which system-related knowledge and tools can find direct applicability in problems of agriculture decision making. In our presentation, we do not attempt to solve particular sequential decision problems, rather to show their structure and that of their solutions as well as point to analysis tools that relate to the feasibility of finding solutions. This has a bearing on infrastructure for data generation. We also attempt to highlight that in order to solve these class of decision problems, data analytics play a key role, but they are not the only ingredient needed to solve the decision problem and determine appropriate sequence of actions.

Without loss of generality, we have excluded from our discussion the spatio-temporal characteristics of crops behaviours, that is, attributes not only change with time and also with space. This gives rise to the so-called spatial variability. We believe that the management of the latter can be achieved by judicious determination of spatial zones within which crop-specific management can be formulated in terms of the sequential decision problems described in this paper.

We hope this paper raises interest in the application of proven tools commonly used in sectors such as economics, process control, and aerospace. We hope also it motivates the new generation of agricultural scientists to interact with experts from other areas and bring new tools into agriculture, for it is at the boundaries of the different disciplines that the highest potential for innovation lies.

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